

Dendrochronological analysis of altarpiece from Slagen church, Norway KHM C2124

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In this report, the dendrochronological analysis of the altarpiece from Slagen church in Norway is described. This research was commissioned to contribute to the research project, 'After the Black Death: Painting and Polychrome Sculpture in Norway, 1350–1550'. The project is co-led by Noëlle Streeton and Tine Frøysaker, based in Conservation Studies, University of Oslo (UiO). Funding for this study was issued to Noëlle Streeton and Kristin Kausland in 2013 by the Department of Archaeology, Conservation and History (IAKH) and the Faculty of Humanities, UiO.

The altarpiece consists of a corpus with backing and sides all of oak planks and adorned with oak tracery and six reliefs also of oak (fig. 1). There are also two wings each consisting again of planking (back and sides), tracery and reliefs, all again made from oak. The sides of the corpus and the wings were painted, so no tree-rings were visible for analysis on these. The backing planks of the corpus, of which there were six, two backing planks from the right wing, a selection of the tracery on the corpus and on both wings and a selection of the reliefs (one from the corpus, one from the left wing and two from the right wing) were suitable for analysis. The reliefs are made from two or more joined wooden elements, so all-in-all 21 components are analysed (eight planks, four tracery elements and four reliefs comprising nine wood components).

Measuring

Measuring of oak for dendrochronology conventionally entails access to the transverse section of the wood, in the case of artworks on oak, by gently cleaning or paring the object to expose the rings. Dendrochronology of art objects is always carried out with minimum damage to the object. Non-invasive analysis is also possible, if the tree-rings are sufficiently exposed on the object. Places where varnish or paint has not been applied, or which has worn away with time can allow non-invasive measurement of the rings. Relatively recently, even objects where the tree-rings are not discernable on the object's surface have been successfully analysed non-invasively. The project team consisted of Jan Bill (Museum of Cultural History, University of Oslo), Øistein Johnsen (Norwegian Geotechnical Institute (NGI)) and Aoife Daly (independent researcher, now at Statens Museum for Kunst (CATS/SMK)) (Bill et al 2012). In this case an industrial CT scanner was used to attain x-ray images of the cross-section of oak objects, mainly from the Gokstad Viking ship burial, that were of a resolution high enough to be able to carry out reliable tree-ring measurements. This method however is only suitable for relatively small objects, and was therefore not applicable in the case of the altarpiece examined here.

Fig. 1. Slagen altarpiece. View of the corpus.

In some wood species with relatively simple anatomy (conifers particularly) measuring can be carried out on the longitudinal section of the timber, but oak has a more complicated structure, making measuring for dendrochronology on the longitudinal section less straightforward.

Fig. 2. Slagen altarpiece. The elements analysed are marked; planks in green, tracery in blue and reliefs in purple.

For the Slagen altarpiece no invasive options were possible, and the objects could not be dismantled for the analysis, so all measurements were to be taken from parts where the wood grain was already exposed. The transverse section of the wood was visible on some of the components of the altarpiece, particularly the carved tracery and reliefs. On the planking however, only the longitudinal section was exposed. In spite of the difficulty that this represents, it was decided nevertheless to experiment with measuring the tree-rings on the longitudinal section, to see if this method could be adopted. Macro photographs of the surfaces, along with a ruler for scale, were taken. These photos were then stitched together using Adobe Photoshop (version

11.0.2), and measured using an application “Able Image Analyser”. Here, the scale is used to calibrate the picture, and the measurements are made to 1/100mm precision. For calculation of the t-value (“t-test”) “CROS” (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used, embedded in the program “DENDRO” (Tyers, 1997). In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed. Ian Tyers, Sheffield and Pascale Fraiture, Brussels, has contributed to this analysis with data comparison and invaluable discussion.

Fig. 3. Slagen altarpiece. Close-up view of the exposed tree-rings on the carved reliefs from the right wing.

The results

As can be seen from the table of internal correlation (table 1), several wood elements had such similar tree-ring curves, that it can be suggested they came from the same tree. Some of these come as little surprise. “Same tree 1” is represented by the two halves of relief 7 on the right wing. “Same tree 2” is represented by two of the three wood elements of relief 9, also on the right wing. “Same tree 3” is actually two separate measurements from plank 4 from the corpus backing, which was accidentally measured twice, from two sets of macro images, showing in fact that measuring from the longitudinal section is producing consistent results, “Same tree 4” is represented by two planks from the corpus backing, planks 2 and 6. Finally, “same tree 5” is

represented by two wood pieces, from two different reliefs; the left element of relief 6 on the corpus and the left element of relief 10 on the left wing

Fig. 4. Slagen altarpiece. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated elements. The colours mark the dating of the different components of the altarpiece; the planks c. AD 1496-1507 (green), the reliefs after c. AD 1498 (purple) and the tracery after c. AD 1505 (blue).

The plank backing

All six backing planks on the corpus and two from the right wing are analysed and all but one are dated. All of these were measured on the longitudinal section (fig. 6), but due to the relatively high number of planks analysed in this way, and because there was a quite good correlation between several of them, a stringent control for inaccuracies could be kept. To estimate the felling date for the trees that the planks were made from, we must allow for missing sapwood. The dendrochronological analysis indicates that the trees had grown in the Southern Baltic region (see below), so it is here appropriate to use a sapwood estimate for the region around the mouth of the Vistula River (c. 15 sapwood years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)). Possible sapwood is noted on plank 3 during examination, but this is not possible to confirm on the macro photographs. Of the planks, this one has the outermost tree-rings preserved, allowing

the possibility that the outer rings indeed are sapwood (see fig. 4). The outermost preserved ring on plank 3 was formed in AD 1495. If it is not sapwood, the felling date for the tree that this plank was made from can be estimated to have taken place after AD 1505. If however the sapwood is correctly identified, the felling date can be placed at c. AD 1496-1507, marked in green in the diagram (fig. 4).

The tracery

Four tracery carvings were also chosen for analysis; one from the corpus, one from the left wing and two from the right wing (see fig. 2). These elements are carved from oak planks. Due to the form that the carving gave these pieces, the tree-rings were clear in both longitudinal and transverse sections (fig. 5), allowing a rigorous control of the tree growth for accurate measurement of the tree-ring series.

All four tracery pieces that were analysed are dated. Due to the quite good correlation between these four pieces, it might be speculated that the trees used for the tracery were felled at the same time. Only heartwood was observed on the tracery. The outermost preserved tree-ring on the four tracery elements is on tracery 7 from the right wing (fig. 2), and this ring was formed in AD 1495. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the trees used for the tracery is estimated to after AD 1505 (see fig. 4).

			Z103013a	Z103003a	Z103005a	Z103006a	Z103009a	Z103010a	Z103004a	Z103007a	Z1030089	Z1030129	Z103016c	Z103017a	Z103018a	Z103002a	Z103022a	Z103020a	Z103015a	Z103019a	Z103021a	
Average Z103M003	plank	Z103013a	*	3.94	1.26	1.27	2.44	-	-	-	-	1.03	-	-	-	-	-	2.16	2.77	2.39	2.94	
	reliefs	Z103003a	3.94	*	4.39	2.85	2.69	1.72	2.07	-	2.86	3.14	3.12	1.10	1.44	2.86	-	2.48	2.61	3.3	3.14	
		same tree1 Z103005&6	1.26	4.39	*	15.83	2.57	2.49	2.34	1.85	3.62	1.63	2.82	1.59	2.55	2.99	2.14	2.77	3.23	\	-	
		Z103006a	1.27	2.85	15.83	*	1.6	1.68	2.09	1.96	3.12	2.18	3.02	1.46	2.19	2.19	2.34	1.8	2.28	\	\	
		same tree2 Z103009&10	Z103009a	2.44	2.69	2.57	1.6	*	11.66	4.12	1.72	2.47	3.54	1.87	1.52	2.37	-	-	-	2.62	2.2	1.01
		Z103010a	-	1.72	2.49	1.68	11.66	*	5.5	3.45	3.56	3.89	2.42	2.31	2.54	-	-	1.87	2.79	2.16	-	
		Z103004a	-	2.07	2.34	2.09	4.12	5.5	*	4.66	3.44	3.18	3.37	1.27	1.50	-	1.11	1.07	-	2.68	-	
		Z103007a	-	-	1.85	1.96	1.72	3.45	4.66	*	6.03	2.74	2.15	3.45	2.97	-	-	-	1.03	-	\	-
		Z1030089	-	2.86	3.62	3.12	2.47	3.56	3.44	6.03	*	5.95	2.76	3.21	4.86	2.24	-	1.15	1.31	1.92	1.6	
	planks	Z1030129	1.03	3.14	1.63	2.18	3.54	3.89	3.18	2.74	5.95	*	2.29	1.09	2.91	-	-	2	2.85	2.57	1.05	
		Z103016c	-	3.12	2.82	3.02	1.87	2.42	3.37	2.15	2.76	2.29	*	3.28	4.07	-	-	-	1.28	1.11	1.37	1.86
		same tree3 Z103017&18	Z103017a	-	1.10	1.59	1.46	1.52	2.31	1.27	3.45	3.21	1.09	3.28	*	9.70	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Z103018a	-	1.44	2.55	2.19	2.37	2.54	1.50	2.97	4.86	2.91	4.07	9.70	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.45
	reliefs	same tree5 Z103002&22	Z103002a	-	2.86	2.99	2.19	-	-	-	-	2.24	-	-	-	-	*	10.89	4.94	2.43	2.24	-
		Z103022a	-	-	2.14	2.34	-	-	1.11	-	-	-	-	-	-	10.89	*	3.14	1.2	2.21	1.94	
	planks	same tree4 Z103 15&20	Z103020a	2.16	2.48	2.77	1.8	-	1.87	1.07	1.03	1.15	2	1.28	-	4.94	3.14	*	11.67	3.39	1.63	
		Z103015a	2.77	2.61	3.23	2.28	2.62	2.79	-	-	1.31	2.85	1.11	-	-	2.43	1.2	11.67	*	4.07	2.07	
		Z103019a	2.39	3.3	\	\	2.2	2.16	2.68	\	1.92	2.57	1.37	-	-	2.24	2.21	3.39	4.07	*	3.9	
		Z103021a	2.94	3.14	-	\	1.01	-	-	-	1.6	1.05	1.86	-	1.45	-	1.94	1.63	2.07	3.9	*	

Table 1. Slagen altarpiece. The table shows the correlation (t-value) between the dated tree-ring curves from the wooden elements analysed from the altarpiece. The grey tone highlights the high t-values. The colours mark the different components of the altarpiece; blue for the tracery, purple for the reliefs and green for the planks.

Fig. 5. Slagen altarpiece. Close-up view of the exposed tree-rings on one of the carved tracery pieces from the right wing.

The reliefs

Finally, four reliefs from the corpus and the wings were chosen for analysis; one from the corpus, one from the left wing and two from the right wing (again see fig. 2). Three of the reliefs were made from two wood elements, a left and a right almost equally sized, while one, relief 9, comprised three wood elements. Again the form of the carvings allowed the tree-rings to be seen in transverse section (fig. 3), allowing accurate and reliable measurement of the tree-ring series. All but one of the wood components from the reliefs are dated. The undated one (the narrow right hand wood element on relief 9, numbered Z103011a) contained just 58 rings. The analysis suggests that the two components of relief 7 are from the same tree (same tree 1) and the two dated parts of relief 9 are also from the same tree (same tree 2). Two wood pieces from two different reliefs; the left element of relief 6 on the corpus and the left element of relief 10 on the left wing are also probably from the same tree (same tree 5). There is a striking degree of variation in the choice of oaks for the reliefs, in terms of the correlation between the trees and the speed at which the trees, that were used, have grown. “Same tree 1” is a fast-grown oak, with an average ring width of 2.8 mm, while “same tree 2” grew at a much slower rate, averaging 1.2 mm per year. Although

the wood for the reliefs come from the Southern Baltic region (see provenance below) their variation might indicate that they are from different sources within that region. Only heartwood has been observed on the reliefs analysed. The outermost preserved and measured ring on the objects as a group was formed in AD 1488, and this ring is preserved on two of the wood elements (relief 9, mid element (Z103009a) and relief 6, left element (Z103022a). Allowing for the missing sapwood, the felling date for the trees used for the reliefs is estimated at after c. AD 1498.

Oak provenance

The correlation between all the dated elements from the Slagen altarpiece is shown in table 1. An average of all these (Z103M003), representing 14 trees is 262 years in length and covers the period AD 1234-1495. The correlation (t-test) between this average and a range of tree-ring data for oak is shown in table 2. The tree-ring average achieves highest correlation with a range of tree-ring datasets that are known to be from oak that grew in the Southern Baltic region including data from artworks (e.g. Hillam & Tyers 1995) and from other objects shown, through dendrochronology, to be made from Baltic imports. The oaks for the Slagen altarpiece grew in the Southern Baltic region.

Fig. 6. Slagen altarpiece. Close-up view of the exposed tree-rings in longitudinal section, on one of the backing planks on the corpus.

Conclusion

A completely non-invasive dendrochronological analysis of the Slagen altarpiece has been successful here, allowing a range of details about the wood used in the structure to be attained. The technique is much more time consuming than conventional measurement where the object is cleaned to expose the rings, but especially where the transverse section is exposed, reliable analysis is shown to be possible here. Questions that remain of the material include the identification of sapwood, and this is a very important point in the interpretation of the dating result here. If the presence of sapwood is indeed confirmed and if we take the whole material to have been felled at the same time, we can combine the felling estimates for all trees in the analysis. This would mean that the felling of the trees for the altarpiece can have taken place c. AD 1505-1507.

If this is not sapwood, then a less precise dating for the material as a whole, at after around 1505 is the result. If we speculate, however, that not much more than the sapwood rings were trimmed off the timber in the making of the altarpiece, we might suggest a date for the felling of the trees used to make the altarpiece, at c. AD 1510-20. The time between tree felling (transport and seasoning) to manufacture is not accounted for here.

As we do not have sapwood or bark edge preserved on the timber, it is impossible to say whether the procurement of the timber was a single felling event. However, as the correlation between the tree-ring curves from the different elements and the variation in the growth rate of the trees used suggests, the oaks are not from a single source, but rather reflect selection of material from a range of locations within the Southern Baltic region.

Filenames	-	-	Z103M003	
-	start	dates	AD1234	
-	dates	end	AD1495	
na_07	AD1340	AD1517	7.76	Newton Abbot panel (Tyers pers comm)
os243u	AD1303	AD1504	7.47	Adriaen Isenbrandt St Barbara (Tyers pers comm)
0M040005	AD1257	AD1615	7.33	Baltic 2 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
os694bu	AD1300	AD1523	7.30	Stephen Gardiner Oxford (Tyers pers comm)
os603bc	AD1353	AD1574	7.20	Henry VII (Tyers pers comm)
os059_12	AD1295	AD1434	7.19	Kent Boughton Monchelsea Chest board (Tyers pers comm)
0M040004	AD1156	AD1597	7.12	Baltic 1 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
Z084M001	AD1309	AD1435	7.12	Skaftö wreck barrel (Daly 2013)
os181	AD1280	AD1505	7.01	Soc Antiqs Ferdinand (Tyers pers comm)
hap054	AD1318	AD1515	6.98	Bies La montée au calvaire (Fraiture pers comm)
os884_tp2	AD1341	AD1481	6.97	Winchester St Cross tracery panel (Tyers pers comm)
p212d	AD1357	AD1506	6.74	Déluge (Fraiture pers comm)
os842ar	AD1281	AD1518	6.61	Westerham board (Tyers pers comm)
hap106b	AD1326	AD1514	6.55	Bosch Tentation de saint Antoine (Fraiture pers comm)
HEADSx11	AD1304	AD1521	6.47	Stirling heads, Baltic (Crone pers comm)
Z101M001	AD1317	AD1493	6.34	Kværfjord altertavle Norge planks same tree (Daly)
stirlingdoors	AD1270	AD1524	6.23	Stirling doors, Baltic (Crone pers comm)
B019M002	AD1374	AD1574	6.17	Helsingør Kulturværft barrels (Daly 2009)
Z076m003	AD1097	AD1393	6.16	Skjernøysund ship & cargo (Daly 2011)
0628021M	AD1256	AD1443	5.84	Torun Joh K (Wazny pers comm)
GAPCX7	AD1283	AD1450	5.68	Guthrie Aisle panels (Crone pers comm)
0075M0032	AD1221	AD1456	5.53	Vejdyb ship (Daly 1997)
P815001M	AD1262	AD1503	5.44	Bielsk Podl. (Wazny pers comm)
HMC_T165	AD1078	AD1369	5.42	Hull boards from coffins Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm)
0EQKTVM0	AD1295	AD1549	5.30	Tallinn Christ Money-lenders (Daly & Lääneld 2012)
H11EOM01	AD1260	AD1495	5.25	Bordesholmer Altar (Hamburg Uni. revised Daly 2007)
P0011009	AD1103	AD1403	5.12	Copper Ship- Wainscot (Wazny pers comm)
P720404M	AD1192	AD1452	5.02	Pultusk (Wazny pers comm)

Table 2. Slagen altarpiece, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the average tree-ring curve (Z103M003) from the wood elements that make up the piece and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Literature

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filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra start	extra end	interpretation / felling
Z103001a	Slagen altertavle Norge left wing top relief 10 right element	97			O	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z103002a	Slagen altertavle Norge left wing top relief 10 left element SAME TREE 5	139	AD1346	AD1484	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1498
Z103003a	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus bottom right relief 6 right element	199	AD1254	AD1452	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1462
Z103004a	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus top left tracery 1	122	AD1358	AD1479	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1489
Z103005a	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing top relief 7 right element SAME TREE 1	83	AD1395	AD1477	O	G	0	N	H2	H1	after AD1489
Z103006a	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing top relief 7 left element SAME TREE 1	78	AD1403	AD1480	O	G	0	N	H10	N	after AD1489
Z103007a	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing top tracery 7	111	AD1385	AD1495	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1505
Z1030089	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing middle tracery 8	125	AD1351	AD1475	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1485
Z103009a	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing bottom relief 9 mid element SAME TREE 2	199	AD1290	AD1488	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1498
Z103010a	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing bottom relief 9 left element SAME TREE 2	158	AD1327	AD1484	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1498
Z103011a	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing bottom relief 9 right element	58			O	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z1030129	Slagen altertavle Norge left wing mid tracery 11	147	AD1348	AD1494	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1504
Z103013a	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing back panel 3	167	AD1293	AD1459	R	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1469
Z103014a	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus back plank 1	75			T	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z103015a	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus back plank 2 SAME TREE 4	121	AD1359	AD1479	R	G	0	N	H1	H2	after AD1492
Z103016c	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus back plank 3	143	AD1353	AD1495	R	G	12	N	H1	H1	after AD1505
Z103017a	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus back plank 4 SAME TREE 3	136	AD1337	AD1472	R	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1482
Z103018a	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus back plank 4 SAME TREE 3	128	AD1344	AD1471	R	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1482
Z103019a	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus back plank 5	173	AD1234	AD1406	T	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1416
Z103020a	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus back plank 6 SAME TREE 4	116	AD1367	AD1482	T	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1492
Z103021a	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing back panel 1	154	AD1315	AD1468	R	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1478
Z103022a	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus bottom right relief 6 left element SAME TREE 5	114	AD1375	AD1488	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1498
Z103005&6 same tree 1	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing top relief same tree left and right elements	86	AD1395	AD1480	O	G	0	N	N	N	after AD1489
Z103009&10 same tree 2	Slagen altertavle Norge right wing bottom relief mid element	199	AD1290	AD1488	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1498
Z103017&18 same tree 3	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus back plank 4 & 5 same tree	136	AD1337	AD1472	R	G	0	N	N	N	after AD1482
Z103015&20 same tree 4	Slagen altertavle Norge corpus back plank 2&6	124	AD1359	AD1482	?	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1492
Z103002&22 same tree 5	Slagen altertavle Norge reliefs 10 & 6	143	AD1346	AD1488	O	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1498
Z103M003	Slagen altertavle Norge 14 timber mean	262	AD1234	AD1495							

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.
Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.

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Table 3. Slagen altarpiece, Oslo. List of objects analysed.